

Fear of Missing Out on Sleep Disturbance and Cognitive Performance

**Muhammed Sinan ,Research Student (SIA Vakery),
Contact: sinumuhammad33@gmail.com**

Introduction:

The rise of a fully connected world has established a phenomenon that sculpts our everyday existence, as well as our sleep and cognitive functions. The idea of FOMO—the fear of missing out—has developed consciously to become part and parcel of modern society, all the more considering social media and connectivity 24/7. FOMO is defined as a fear of pervasive anxiety that others might be having rewarding experiences one may be absent from. Further, it can lead to compulsive checking of social media, excessive digital engagement with all its devices, and a constant need to stay connected, usually at the expense of sleep and cognitive well-being.

In this paper, we explain how FOMO goes in tandem with sleep disturbance and impaired cognitive function. We are going to explain the psychology that underlies FOMO, its interference with sleep, and consequently its interference with various mental procedures. Respectively, one will be able to see the need to deal with FOMO and let an individual put more emphasis on sleep for ideal cognitive functioning and general health.

1. Understanding Fear of Missing Out

1.1 Definition and Origins

FOMO, or Fear of Missing Out, is a relatively new term that has made huge waves in both popular culture and in academic research. Although the concept had been described in 1996 by psychologist Dan Herman, it wasn't until 2004, in an op-ed by Patrick McGinnis for The Harbus, Harvard Business School's student newspaper, that the term "FOMO" was actually coined.

FOMO can be defined as an apprehension that others are having rewarding experiences from which the apprehender is absent. An age of social anxiety, FOMO is characterized by a desire to stay continually connected with what others are doing.

Though missing out is not an entirely new notion, the advent of social media and smartphones accelerated it to previously unimaginable levels.

1.2 Psychological Mechanisms Behind FOMO

Several psychological theories explain the underlying mechanisms for FOMO:

a) Self-Determination Theory: According to this theory, the unsatisfied basic psychological needs to competence, autonomy, and relatedness are among the causes of the underlying mechanisms of FOMO. If that is the case, wherein the basic needs are not satisfied in real life, then that is the time when people may turn to social media and constant connectivity in order to meet up with these needs.

b. Social Comparison Theory: Argued by Leon Festinger, the theory posits that a human tends to compare themselves relatively with other people's opinions and abilities. Using that in the parlance of FOMO, the flow of information from social media remains a constant, laying grounds for such comparisons, which most often result in feelings of inadequacy or anxiety.

c) Cognitive Dissonance Theory: The theory stipulates that a person is likely to attain cognitive consonance among beliefs and actions. If wanting to partake in social activities conflicts with other obligations, such as working or sleeping, then the FOMO could be creating cognitive dissonance. Feelings of unease and nervousness are then generated.

1.3 FOMO in the Digital Age

More than anything else, the digital revolution has hugely intensified FOMO. By further elaborating, social media sets a virtual platform where people are exposed to social events, successes, and happenings of other individuals in a near-relentless manner. In this regard, the constant feeds regarding social events, successes, and happenings can easily elevate the feeling of being left out and enhance the urgency of constant connectivity.

Here are the biggest contributing factors for FOMO in a digital age:

a) Always connected: If a person has a smartphone and mobile internet, then that person is always connected to social media and messaging apps, never letting him switch off.

b) Social Media Algorithms: This set of algorithms was prepared to keep as many users online as possible, seeing the most interesting or popular content, hence increasing the effect of FOMO.

c) Digital Peer Pressure: It is an insidious pressure that may develop to be online most of the time; specifically, it is associated with the need to respond to messages and social media immediately.

d) FOMO Marketing: Most businesses and marketers have mastered using this fear to their advantage. Through the generation of a sense of urgency, they are able to drive engagement and sales, which further seals these feelings of FOMO.

2. How FOMO Affects Sleeping Habits

2.1 FOMO and Sleep Procrastination

One of the major ways how FOMO works on sleep is through sleep procrastination. It means delaying bedtime just when one intends to go to sleep, usually because of many digital behaviors and often social media. Further catalyzing this behavior is perhaps the fear of missing out that some relevant social interactions or information might have been missed should one have gone to sleep.

In fact, bed-time procrastinators had a higher degree of FOMO. Indeed, studies made by Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology would infer a strong relationship of late bedtimes with FOMO scores, controlled for age, sex, and quality of sleep.

2.2 Nighttime Social Media use and Sleep interference

FOMO typically triggers late-night social media use, which has at least the following disadvantages for sleep.

a) Delayed Onset of Sleep: Blue light from digital devices lowers the production of melatonin, even making it more difficult to fall asleep.

b) Cognitive Arousal: Involvement in social media can easily provide mental activation, making it hard to wind down before going to sleep.

c) Fragmented Sleep Patterns: Using devices to check upon in the middle of the night could lead to chunk sleeping or fragmented sleep patterns.

d) Lack of Sleep: In general, sleep deprivation usually takes place just by replacing the time used to sleep with social media time.

A recent Sleep article details that individuals who spend a longer time on social media report poor quality of sleep, reduced duration of sleep, and increased sleep instability.

2.3 FOMO and Sleep Quality

In addition to the length of time an individual sleeps for, FOMO may also reduce how quality sleep is. Anxiety and rumination due to FOMO lead to:

a) Sleep Onset Insomnia: The bed partner cannot get to sleep due to the fear of missing a social interaction or anything else.

b) Nocturnal Waking: The anxiety from FOMO results in increased nocturnal wakings by the individual for reasons that have evoked necessarily the urge to reach for the device.

c) Reduced Slow-Wave Sleep: Deep restorative phases of sleep could have been disrupted by increased stress and arousal caused by FOMO.

d) Subjective Sleep Quality Worse: Even in those in whom the duration of sleep was adequate, individuals with FOMO complained of still not being equally well-rested when getting out of bed.

3. The Effects of Sleep Disruption on Cognitive Performance

3.1 General Background on the Role of Sleep in Cognitive Processing

It also deals with the functions already observed, such as memory consolidation, learning, attention, and executive functions. These cardinal processes that sleep cycles undergo have long pointed to its critical role in cognitive performance.

a) Memory Consolidation: Information from short-term memory is transferred to long-term memory during sleep, specifically in slow-wave sleep and REM.

b) Synaptic Homeostasis: Sleep is required to preserve the plasticity of the brain by reducing those synaptic connections that might have been overgrown and enlarging on the other relevant connections.

c) Glymphatic System Function: Sleep allows the brain's glymphatic system to clear metabolic by-products, including waste products related to neurodegenerative diseases.

d) Emotional Regulation: Sleep, in particular REM sleep, is thought to participate in making sense of emotional experiences and in mood regulation.

3.2 Attention and Concentration

This sleep disruption, caused by FOMO-induced behaviors in many instances, impacts attention and concentration greatly:

a) Diminished vigilance: As compared to normals, sleep-deprived subjects have a considerably lower ability to focus on tasks, more so in those tests that require sustained attention.

b) Increments in distractibility: One easily falls prey to irrelevant stimuli, and these increase in sleep deprivation.

c) Selective attention: Pay attention to appropriate stimuli, ignore the others; this is affected by sleep deprivation.

d) Delayed Reaction Times: One of the features of the sleep-deprived person is falling behind in reacting to stimuli. In case one has to make fast decisions, then these become more serious.

3.3 Effect on Learning and Memory

The disturbances of FOMO with sleep hinder normal memory consolidation and learning to occur in the following manner:

a) Encoding: Here, it does influence learning and retention of fresh information in that sleep deprivation impairs the process whereby the brain will lay down new information.

a) Less Consolidation: Poor sleep—lack of slow-wave sleep in particular—may not allow proper transmission of information from short-term to long-term memory.

c) Decreased Recall: Both short- and long-term memory retrieval can be affected by sleep loss, therefore problems in accessing stored information.

d) Impaired Procedural Learning: It appears that during consolidation, sleep is able to play an important role in procedural memories underlying skill acquisition. This could be disturbed by the sleep disruption.

3.4 Effects on Executive Functions

Overall, executive functions are very complex cognitive procedures which include decision making, planning, and, problem solving, being more sensitive to sleep disruption:

a) Impaired Judgment: Sleep-deprived individuals commonly yield to riskier decisions. They cannot access the salient features of a situation and/or appreciate the outcome of one's actions.

b) Impaired Cognitive Flexibility: Both flexibility in reacting to other entities' behavior and task switching are reduced in states lacking adequate sleep.

c) Lower Inhibitory Control: Inhibitory control, which is needed to assist in the suppression of inappropriate responses or actions, may be diminished as a result of sleep loss.

d) Lower Planning and Organization: Good execution is normally impaired in states of deprived sleep by the ability to make good plans and to organize activities.

3.5 Emotional and Social Cognition

FOMO-related sleep disturbance can also be observed on emotional processing and social cognition:

a) Enhanced emotional reactivity in response to negative stimuli: Existing evidence supports the view that sleep loss enhances emotional reactivity to negative stimuli.

b) Impaired emotion recognition: Impairment of the ability to recognize emotional information in others occurs under conditions of sleep deprivation.

c) Decreased empathy: A reduction in empathy and social sensitivity could characterize sleep-deprived subjects.

d) Altered social decision-making: A sleep disorder may impede the perception and reaction to socio-emotional information by individuals and thus probably change the choice of optimal social responsiveness.

4. The Cyclical Relationship of FOMO, Sleep Disruption, and Cognitive Impairment

4.1 The Vicious Cycle

The interrelationship of FOMO, sleep disruption, and cognitive impairment usually manifests itself in the form of a self-perpetuating cycle:

- a) FOMO induces more nighttime usage of social media and later bedtimes.
- b) Such behavior is likely to disrupt sleep and decrease its quality.
- c) Lower sleep quality results in cognitive deficits of low attention and low executive function.
- d) These cognitive deficits can increase the susceptibility to FOMO in that a person is less able to manage the continued use of social media and to process the emotions that result from such use appropriately.
- e) The cycle persists, and therefore, in all likelihood, it deteriorates over time.

4.2. Sleep Disruption, Cognitive Biases, and FOMO

Sleep disruption can contribute to the two cognitive biases involved in the cycle of FOMO. An example is given below:

- a) Negativity Bias:** An exhausted individual probably has a bit of a negative social experience and thus will make stronger a feeling of neglect.

- a) Confirmation Bias:** Sleep deprivation results in the further strengthening of previous predispositions toward, for instance, the use of continuous connection to meet social needs, that is, selective attention to information that confirms these predispositions.

- b) Availability Heuristic:** Sleep disruption may compromise an individual's over-reliance on easily accessible information when they make judgments about social experiences. This can always result in bias in perceptions since it would always be based on available information such as social media feeds.

4.3 Self-Regulation

In this regard, self-regulation takes an important stance in dealing with FOMO and getting good sleep. However, disrupted self-regulation is all that a poor sleep begets at numerous levels:

a) Lowered impulse control: A sleep-deprived individual might find it difficult to delay the impulse to check social media or engage in some other FOMO-driven behavior.

b) Impaired goal-oriented behavior: A good night's sleep, lost due to FOMO, could be translated as a long-term goal of healthy sleep, not being important enough to be a priority than short-term gratifications.

c) Weakened emotional regulation: More damaged sleep might additionally diminish one's ability to control feelings. This might feed right back into the anxiety that was fuelling FOMO in the first place.

5. Breaking the Cycle

5.1 Digital Detox and Boundaries

Digital detox and setting boundaries to the use of technology may reduce some of the effects of FOMO on sleep. The following are the steps toward that:

a) Device-free times: Designated totally device-free time, especially around bedtime, maybe one just switches off; no devices are used at bedtime.

b) Digital Curfews: A firm digital curfew should be established each night in which no digital devices are used.

c) Tech-Free Zones: There should be specific areas within the home, especially the bedroom, that are just plain device-free zones.

d) Periodic Digital Fasts: Spending periods that are long enough to detox from the use of such devices, like staying off social media for a weekend, refreshes the habit and update one's perspective.

5.2 Mindfulness and Cognitive Behavioral Techniques

The following are mindfulness practices and cognitive behavioral techniques that can help in the management of FOMO and improvement of sleep habits:

a) Mindfulness Meditation: This makes an individual increase his or her awareness of what triggers the FOMO, hence responding less reactively.

b) Cognitive Restructuring: A client learns to identify and reappraise thoughts related to FOMO, such as "I will be missing out in case I am not constantly connected."

c) Gratitude Practices: One has to focus on the positive aspects of his or her life. This reduces FOMO that people get from comparing their lives with others'.

d) Acceptance and Commitment Therapy: Such an approach would let one accept uncomfortable feelings due to FOMO and take a commitment towards values-based action, for example sleeping.

5.3 Improvement in Sleep Hygiene

Good sleep hygiene can offset the sleep-disrupting effects of FOMO. This may be achieved through the implementation of the following strategies:

a) Regular sleep timing: The system operates at its finest when it is constantly exposed to a consistent pattern; go to bed and wake up regularly, even on weekends.

b) Sleep-conducive environment: Dark, quiet, and cool.

c) Add some relaxation techniques: Deep breathing or progressive muscle relaxation into the bedtime routine.

d) Caffeine and Alcohol: Consume less of both, at least in the evenings and before going to bed.

5.4 Encouraging Face-to-Face Contact

The more solid offline relationships are, the less the need to replace them by social media and the less FOMO:

a) Arranging Frequent Social Gatherings: Plan regular face-to-face activities so that the need felt for social contact is frequently met.

b) Joining Clubs or Groups: Engage in activities that make one feel part of something based on one's interest.

c) Volunteer: Get involved in community service to enhance the fear of missing out on life's most important events and to make connections outside the social-media realm.

d) Listening Actively: Being able to listen will help to improve the quality of face-to-face interaction.

Greater awareness of the impact that FOMO and sleep disruption are having on cognitive function may itself motivate change:

a) Sleep Education: The effects of sleep regarding cognitive functioning and general health.

b) Media Literacy: Gain the skills for the critical examination of social media and the understanding of the potential negative effect.

c) Time Management Training: Gain the ability to set priorities and rearrange the available time.

d) Share experiences: Talk about FOMO and its effects, which will help in normalizing the experience and 'lessen its power'.

Conclusion:

Recently, FOMO has been one of the major facilitators of sleep disturbance and related cognitive impairments in the genuinely connected contemporary world. Possibly, having information and digital social connections constantly within reach may generate a trait anxiety about possibly missing a reward of some sort. In most cases, such anxiety is a result of a lot of maladaptive behaviors, which include excessive nighttime use of social media and sleep procrastination. These will further disturb sleep and decrease its quality.

This FOMO-induced sleep disturbance is harmful to cognitive function on many levels. Attention, concentration, memory, learning, and executive functions all suffer when sleep is disrupted. Beyond this, it may have the potential to agitate the process of emotional processing and, hence, social cognition, which may only feed back into the very social anxieties that have already started to drive FOMO.

Most of the time, FOMO, sleep disturbance, and cognitive deficit are interlinked and continuously beget a self-perpetuating cycle. Sleep deprivation itself may further enable vulnerability to FOMO because of impaired self-regulation and an increasing number of

cognitive biases regarding what actions will further disturb sleep. A multifaceted approach for breaking this cycle must address both the psychological underpinnings of FOMO and practical ways of improving sleep habits.

Digital detox strategies can supplement it, along with technology boundary setting and the inclusion of mindfulness and sleep hygiene practices, to ensure the least interference of FOMO with sleep and cognitive functioning. It might serve in building real-world connections and enhance an understanding of the importance of sleep and bad impacts resulting from increased social media usage to make greater decisions regarding digital habits.

As our society struggles with the consequences of being always connected, it is even more critical that we both understand and intervene on FOMO's contributions to sleep disruption and cognitive impairments. The acknowledgment of being disconnected from ubiquitous technologies and the priority of sleep have to, by consequence, be intertwined into individual routines in order to provide for better cognitive functioning and general better well-being.

In the end, this does not mean the abandonment of social media or digital devices, but a balance with them so that meaningful social connection is possible without compromising other physiological needs, such as sleep. In the near future, the rapidly studied field will mandate that stakeholders know a great deal about the complex interplay between digital behavior, sleep, and cognition, and how to bring on technology use while protecting cognitive health.

Certainly. Here's a list of references that could be used to support the content of the article. Please note that as an AI, I don't have access to a real-time database of academic publications, so these references are based on my training data and may not represent the most recent research. Always verify these sources and consider updating them with more recent studies when using this content.

References:

1. Przybylski, A. K., Murayama, K., DeHaan, C. R., & Gladwell, V. (2013). *Motivational, emotional, and behavioral correlates of fear of missing out*. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(4), 1841-1848.
2. Beyens, I., Frison, E., & Eggermont, S. (2016). *"I don't want to miss a thing": Adolescents' fear of missing out and its relationship to adolescents' social needs, Facebook use, and Facebook related stress*. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 64, 1-8.

3. Scott, H., & Woods, H. C. (2018). *Fear of missing out and sleep: Cognitive behavioural factors in adolescents' nighttime social media use*. *Journal of Adolescence*, 68, 61-65.
4. Durmer, J. S., & Dinges, D. F. (2005). *Neurocognitive consequences of sleep deprivation*. *Seminars in Neurology*, 25(1), 117-129.
5. Walker, M. P. (2009). *The role of sleep in cognition and emotion*. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1156(1), 168-197.
6. Lemola, S., Perkinson-Gloor, N., Brand, S., Dewald-Kaufmann, J. F., & Grob, A. (2015). *Adolescents' electronic media use at night, sleep disturbance, and depressive symptoms in the smartphone age*. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 44(2), 405-418.
7. Hysing, M., Pallesen, S., Stormark, K. M., Jakobsen, R., Lundervold, A. J., & Sivertsen, B. (2015). *Sleep and use of electronic devices in adolescence: results from a large population-based study*. *BMJ Open*, 5(1), e006748.
8. Goel, N., Rao, H., Durmer, J. S., & Dinges, D. F. (2009). *Neurocognitive consequences of sleep deprivation*. *Seminars in Neurology*, 29(4), 320-339.
9. Krause, A. J., Simon, E. B., Mander, B. A., Greer, S. M., Saletin, J. M., Goldstein-Piekarski, A. N., & Walker, M. P. (2017). *The sleep-deprived human brain*. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 18(7), 404-418.
10. Alhola, P., & Polo-Kantola, P. (2007). *Sleep deprivation: Impact on cognitive performance*. *Neuropsychiatric Disease and Treatment*, 3(5), 553-567.
11. Diekelmann, S., & Born, J. (2010). *The memory function of sleep*. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 11(2), 114-126.